

and confined in a mylar cage for 4 h with 10 viruliferous GLH adults per seedling. The GLH adults were given 3 d of access on TN1 plants doubly infected with RTBV and RTSV to acquire both viruses prior to inoculation. We took 5-cm-long strips of the 2d and 3d youngest leaves of each seedling 2-3 wk after inoculation to detect RTSV by ELISA.

In Utri Merah/TN1, the F₃ progenies segregated into 62 resistant plants (RTSV infection was 0-20%), 66 segregating (21-75%), and 13 susceptible (76-100%) (see table), resulting in a good fit to a 7:8:1 ratio (see figure). The F₁ plants of Utri Merah/TN1 were susceptible to RTSV infection, clearly indicating that

Utri Merah has two recessive genes for resistance to RTSV.

The F₃ analysis in TN1/Utri Rajapan gave a segregation ratio of 1:3 and that in Pankhari 203/TN1 a 1:2:1 ratio, indicating monogenic control of resistance in both Utri Rajapan and Pankhari 203. The F₁ plants of the TN1/Utri Rajapan were susceptible to RTSV while those of Pankhari 203/TN1 showed an intermediate infection rate.

The allelism test between Utri Merah and Utri Rajapan revealed no segregation of F₃ progenies for susceptibility. The F₁ plants were resistant to RTSV infection. This suggests that the recessive gene in Utri Rajapan is the same as one of the two recessive genes in Utri Merah.

The F₃ lines of Utri Rajapan/Pankhari 203 also showed no segregation for susceptibility to RTSV infection and the F₁ plants were likewise resistant, suggesting the presence of the same gene that controls RTSV resistance in Pankhari 203. The inconsistency of dominance of both cultivars could be explained by a dominant GLH resistance gene in Pankhari 203, *Glh-1*, which might suppress RTSV infection.

From these findings, we propose two gene symbols: *tsv-1*, for a gene for RTSV resistance that is common in the three cultivars, and *tsv-2*, for the other gene in Utri Merah that may be used in breeding programs to diversify gene sources for RTSV resistance. ■

Pest resistance— insects

Gall midge biotype 5 identified in Moncompu, Kerala, India

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Four biotypes (1-4) of the Asian rice gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae*) (Wood-Mason) from different rice-growing areas of India have been identified and evaluated. Many gall midge-resistant rice donors and cultures were susceptible at Moncompu, a gall midge-endemic area.

We evaluated 10 differentials in three major groups and susceptible check Taichung Native 1 (TN1), all with known reactions to the biotypes, during 1991-92 wet seasons. The entries were transplanted in early June and late June to allow for peak gall midge infestation. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 3-m rows for each variety at 15 × 15-cm spacing. Percentage of plant and tiller damage was recorded at 50 d after transplanting (DAT).

Potential donors Eswarakora (group 1) and Siam 29 (group 2) showed little damage while Velluthacheera (group 3) exhibited more damage. Up to 85% plant damage was recorded in TN1 (see table).

Reaction of promising cultivars to gall midge biotype 5. Moncompu, Kerala, India. 1991-92 wet seasons.

Group	Entry	Differential	Mean infestation for two seasons		
			Damaged plants (%)	Silvershoots (%)	
I	1	W1263	5.0	4.0	
	2	ARC6605	27.5	5.2	
	II	3	Phalguna	2.5	3.6
		4	ARC5984	2.6	4.6
III	5	CR-MR1523	40.4	12.3	
	6	Velluthacheera	37.5	10.9	
	7	Aganni	40.0	22.9	
	8	Ptb10	37.5	12.8	
	9	T1477	43.1	22.1	
IV	10	TN1	85.0	29.5	

Gall midge populations at Moncompu, Kerala, tend to be distinctly different from the four biotypes characterized earlier. They have been designated as

biotype 5, with the characteristic R-R-S-S pattern for the four groups of differentials. ■

Inheritance of whitebacked planthopper resistance

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We studied the mode of inheritance for resistance to the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) in six resistant local cultivars of rice in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam.

Seedlings at the one-leaf stage were artificially infested with second- and third-instar WBPH nymphs. Reactions of the seedlings were recorded when the susceptible check, Taichung Native 1

(TN1), was completely killed. Seedlings were scored as resistant when they showed reactions similar to those of the resistant check, and as susceptible when they were completely killed or severely stunted with signs of wilting. The reactions of F₁ and F₃ lines were scored on a row basis, while F₂ populations were scored on an individual seedling basis. For the F₃ lines, rows were scored as homozygous resistant, segregating, or homozygous susceptible.

The F₁ seedlings in all crosses were resistant, indicating that resistance was dominant in all six cultivars. The F₂

Table 1. Reaction to whitebacked planthopper of F₁ and F₂ populations from crosses of rice cultivars with TN1. University of Cantho, Vietnam, 1993.

Cross	F ₁ reaction	F ₂ seedlings				χ ²			P		
		Total (no.)	Resistant (no.)	Susceptible (no.)	(%)	3:1	15:1	13:3	3:1	15:1	13:3
TN1/IR2035-117-3	R	1379	1292	87	6	256.94	0.008	140.11	<0.01	90-95	<0.01
TN1/BR46	R	1471	1196	275	18	31.19	388.81	0.003	<0.01	<0.01	90-95
TN1/Xoai Cat	R	1468	1193	275	18	30.75	390.40	0.0003	<0.01	<0.01	95-99
TN1/Base	R	1221	912	309	25	0.06	756.79	34.46	80-90	<0.01	<0.01
TN1/Keo Cha A	R	1220	910	310	25	0.11	764.35	35.52	80-69	<0.01	<0.01
TN1/Rong Lem	R	1351	1005	346	25	0.27	864.26	41.74	60-70	<0.01	<0.01
TN1/La	R	1227	915	312	23	0.12	770.18	35.92	70-75	<0.01	<0.01

Table 2. Reaction to whitebacked planthopper of F₃ lines from crosses of rice cultivars with TN1. University of Cantho, Vietnam, 1993.

Cross	F ₃ lines (no.)				χ ²		P	
	Total	Resistant	Segregating	Susceptible	1:2:1	7:8:1	1:2:1	7:8:1
TN1/IR2035-117-3	335	147	167	21	94.79	0.003	<0.01	>99
TN1/BR46	334	150	162	22	98.41	0.31	<0.01	80-90
TN1/Xoai Cat	328	147	159	22	95.58	0.35	<0.01	80-90
TN1/Base	372	97	185	90	0.27	218.21	80-90	<0.01
TN1/Keo Cha A	374	95	181	98	0.43	267.22	75-85	<0.01
TN1/Rong Lem	363	90	177	96	0.42	266.83	75-85	<0.01
TN1/La	350	89	180	81	0.65	186.80	65-75	<0.01

populations from the crosses of TN1 with Base, Rong Lem, Keo Cha A, and La segregated in the ratio of 3 resistant to 1 susceptible, indicating that a single dominant gene confers resistance (Table 1).

In the cross TN1/IR2035-117-3, the F₂ populations segregated in the ratio of 15 resistant to 1 susceptible, indicating that two dominant genes governed resistance. The F₂ populations of the crosses of TN1/BR46 and TN1/Xoai Cat segregated in

the ratio of 13:3, suggesting that resistance in the two varieties was governed by one dominant and one recessive gene.

The results from the F₃ progenies confirmed the conclusion drawn from the F₂ data (Table 2). In all crosses, except TN1/Xoai Cat, TN1/BR46, and TN1/IR2035-117-3, the observed data agreed with the 1:2:1 resistant, segregating, susceptible ratio expected for monogenic control of resistance. The F₃ data from crosses of TN1/IR2035-117-3, TN1/BR46, and TN1/Xoai Cat agreed with the 7:8:1 ratio expected for digenic control of resistance. ■

Ratnagiri 3: a new gall midge-resistant, late-maturing variety from Maharashtra, India

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Gall midge incidence is a constraint that limits rice production in some areas. We undertook a program to develop high-yielding gall midge-resistant rice genotypes that mature late.

Cultivar Ratnagiri 3 was bred from the cross CR57-MR-1523/IR36/RTN 68. Maharashtra State released it for general cultivation in 1994. It is a semitall, long-duration variety (142 d) with long, bold grains.

In station trials from 1984 to 1986, Ratnagiri 3 outyielded the check variety in gall midge-endemic areas. In multi-location trials from 1987 to 1989, and

Table 1. Grain yield of Ratnagiri 3. Maharashtra, India. 1984-92.

Trial	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Ratnagiri 3 (RTN121)	Check ^a variety
Station trials, 1984-86 wet season	4.1	3.1
Multilocation trials, 1987-89 wet season (8 locations)	4.4	3.9
All India Coordinated Yield Trial	4.2	3.7
MRVT ^b 4 1988 wet season (12 locations)		
Field trial 1990-92 (34 locations)	4.4	3.5

^aVikram for station trials, Ratnagiri 68 for multilocation trials, Pankaj for MRVT 4, and Vidram for field trials. ^bMRVT = multiresistant variety trial.

Table 2. Ratnagiri 3 reactions to pests and diseases in multiresistant variety trial 4, 12 locations,^a 1988 wet season.

Variety	Reaction ^b						
	Disease				Insect pest		
	Blast	Bacterial leaf blight	Sheath blight	Brown spot	Gall midge 1	Gall midge 4	Stem borer
Ratnagiri 3	R	MR	MR	MR	R	R	MR
Pankaj	MR	S	MR	S	S	S	MR

^aLocations had high disease or insect pest pressure. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.